

VETERINARY SCIENCES

EQUIPMENT FOR WATERING DONKEYS

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ABSTRACT

The domestic donkey (*Equus asinus asinus* L.) needs to drink 8-10 liters of water per 100 kg of body weight daily. While it can survive without food for 30-40 days, without water it can only last for 7-8 days. The water it drinks must be clean and fresh.

A donkey will remain thirsty but will not drink water that is not organoleptically acceptable. Watering can be done using containers of various shapes, depending on whether the donkeys are kept as pets at home or in larger numbers on a farm. The containers must be clean, and the water in them must be fresh.

Keywords: Watering, donkey, pasture.

Introduction

The domestic donkey (*Equus asinus asinus* L.) originates from the wild African donkey. The geographical regions where wild donkeys come from are quite harsh. In such conditions, donkeys do not have the opportunity to consume food and water daily. Adult wild donkeys do not need to drink water every day. Only mothers with foals go to the watering hole every day to meet their water needs. Other adult individuals go to the watering holes every 2-3 days (10). The distances they must travel to reach water can sometimes be several dozen kilometers.

During rainy periods, water is significantly more abundant, and watering holes are closer. At such times, wild donkeys travel 3-7 km to water. When they reach water, they can drink up to 30 liters. They usually go to

the watering holes from the evening hours until midnight, although some individuals go to the watering hole in the morning hours. In any case, they go to the water source when the temperature is somewhat lower than it is during the day.

The origin of water

Water in nature exists in three forms: a) atmospheric, b) surface, and c) groundwater. In areas where there are no surface and groundwater sources, water supply is ensured by collecting atmospheric water after precipitation. Water is collected in tanks. The quality of atmospheric water is lower than that of groundwater (4). The cistern includes a collection surface, a purification device, and a reservoir. It must have a ventilation opening as well as a device for pumping water from the reservoir.

Picture 1. Schematic diagram of a cistern (Hrgović, 1979)

The collection surface must logically be flat, smooth, and clean. It is typically made of concrete.

Before water reaches the cistern, it passes through a filter that prevents impurities from entering. Such

cisterns are often positioned at an elevated location so that water exits by gravity. This water, due to its lower mineral content, has a specific taste that domestic animals, including donkeys, particularly dislike. However, when there is no other water available, they will con

When it comes to surface waters, the situation is significantly easier. Such waters are usually available in sufficient quantities, have a good taste, and appropriate temperature. Groundwater needs to be brought to the surface to be usable. For supplying donkeys with water, it is obtained from wells dug into the ground. These wells can be: dug, drilled, spring, artesian, and sub-artesian. The type of well varies depending on the terrain and the depth at which the water is located some it. When the water table is high, wells are dug. As for drilled wells, they can be constructed on any type of terrain. Today, drilling techniques and technology are so advanced that they can reach any depth of groundwater. Reni wells are a combination of dug and drilled wells. Water is brought to the surface using a pump device installed on each reni well. Artesian wells utilize the pressure under which water is found at depth underground to bring water to the surface. When the borehole reaches such water, it flows to the surface under pressure.

Domestic Donkey

Picture 2. The facility for donkeys to stay in if the winter is too cold (Foto.M.Urošević)

Unlike most other domestic animals, which require housing in well-enclosed spaces during the winter, donkeys can be housed in more modest conditions. It is not uncommon for them to have only a simple shelter. This allows them to stay dry in case of precipitation.

The technically simplest way of watering is through automatic waterers, which are supplied with

The descendant of the wild donkey, our domestic donkey, usually does not live in such harsh conditions as its wild ancestor. Water is essential for the normal maintenance of life functions. In the event that an individual does not consume food, it can survive for 30-40 days, losing 50% of its body fat in the process. However, if it lacks water, it perishes within 4-8 days (8). A donkey requires 8-10 liters of water per 100 kg of body weight (3). When considering the watering of donkeys, as well as other domestic animals, two periods must be distinguished:

1. Donkeys are in the stable
2. Donkeys are free on pasture

For each animal species, the primary intention is to reduce the cost of feeding and the number of days spent in the stable. Depending on the weather and climatic conditions, donkeys are on free pasture for about 8-9 months. The more time they spend on pasture, the greater the profitability of the production.

Housing and Watering in the Stable

Despite originating from Africa, a very warm region, the domestic donkey has undergone a highly successful period of acclimatization during domestication. This allows it to withstand significantly lower temperatures than those in its original habitat without any problems. While it is true that nights in Africa are quite cold, there are no cold rains, snow, or frost.

water via pipelines. Often, the water is too cold. The optimal water temperature should be between 15-25°C. During cold days, in open stables, which are often used for donkeys, the water in automatic waterers tends to be colder. Donkeys do not drink cold water, nor do they drink overheated water.

Picture 3. Most of the year, if the winter is not too cold, a shelter is sufficient for the donkeys. Baroque donkeys under the shelter. (Foto: M.Nemecek)

Another problem with watering cup arises during cold days when the air temperature drops below freezing. The water in the pipelines freezes, as does the water left in the waterer. Donkeys cannot use it. By licking the ice in the waterer when they are thirsty, they can only catch a cold. Another problem with automatic waterers is the introduction of food into the waterer, as

shown in the following photo. When the water is not clean, donkeys will not drink it. They remain thirsty but will not drink dirty water.

In regions without cold winters, water can be offered to donkeys in concrete troughs. In such cases, water is usually supplied to the troughs from the pipelines via a hose.

Picture 4. Automatic waterer filled with hay on a farm in Cyprus (foto: M.Urošević)

Picture 5. Stone troughs, farm in Cyprus (foto:M.Urošević)

In regions with a continental climate where winters are somewhat colder, donkeys do not require special stable facilities. It is important that snow does

not fall on them. In the next photo is one such structure in the "Zasavica" Nature Park in Serbia. Automatic waterers are installed but the donkeys do not use them.

Picture 6. Automatic water dispenser, Zasavica, Nature Park, Serbia (foto:M:Urošević)

When there are 1-2 donkeys on a small farm, a common solution for water supply is a trough, often made of concrete. These troughs are stable, cannot be

overturned, and typically have low walls so that other livestock in the vicinity can also drink from them.

Picture 7. Concrete watering trough for donkeys and livestock in Macedonia (foto: M. Urošević)

Such low troughs for watering have a significant issue with water contamination. If livestock, especially ducks and geese, are present, they enter the water and pollute it. Donkeys refuse to drink dirty water; they will remain thirsty rather than drink contaminated water.

When it comes to individual owners with a small number of animals, they water their donkeys in various ways. One effective method is to have water containers fixed or attached to the wall. This setup prevents them from being overturned and ensures a stable water supply for the animals.

Picture 8. Fixed water containers (Foto: M. Nemecek)

Practical experience suggests that it is beneficial to place a firm surface in front of such fixed water containers. When donkeys drink water, almost always, they spill a certain amount outside the container with their last few sips. This water then falls onto the ground, making the surface damp and soft. Donkeys generally dislike soft surfaces because they can sink in and

potentially injure their hooves. Additionally, moist hooves can lead to softening of the hoof horn, making them more susceptible to injuries on harder surfaces. Such lesions on the hoof horn provide an ideal entry point for numerous microorganisms, especially anaerobic bacteria.

Picture 9. Watering containers with a wooden platform in front allow donkeys to stand on it while drinking water. This setup keeps their hooves dry and prevents the ground from becoming wet and soft, which could otherwise lead to hoof problems. (Foto: M.Nemecek)

In the provided watering containers for donkeys, algae are visible on the water surface. Algae are not a problem; they act as biological cleaners, filtering the water. Donkeys willingly drink water even with algae present. In the case of an individual farm with up to 5 donkeys, each donkey should be provided with its own watering container. Each individual prefers to have its own water container. If there are more than 5 donkeys, they are watered in groups. This means they drink water from a shared concrete, plastic, or metal trough. Since donkeys are highly social animals and respect hierarchy, it is important to ensure the trough is long enough for the donkeys to have enough space when they stand to drink water. Based on our practical observations, we suggest calculating 0.70 cm per donkey along the length of the trough. We emphasize

that this is a proposal for group watering of donkeys on an individual farm with no more than 10 donkeys. If there is the possibility of accessing the trough from both sides, donkeys will gladly distribute themselves on both sides of the trough.

If the number of donkeys exceeds 10, it is considered a larger population. In this case, not all donkeys will come to drink water at the same time. There is a hierarchy, and it is known in what order each donkey goes to drink water. If there are no other animals in the yard, especially poultry, and if it's not near the place where donkeys get their hay, the water container can be placed on the ground. This way, the possibility of contamination is minimized, and the water remains clean.

Picture 10. Watering from a container on the ground (photo: S. Faschling)

The water in these containers must be fresh. During hot summer days, the water heats up quickly, so the water containers should, if possible, be placed in the shade. Fresh water should be provided daily. During winter, there is the opposite process and problem. Water freezes. If there is ice in the water container, it must be removed, and of course, cold water should not be added as it is during summer.

Watering on pasture

As previously mentioned, the profitability of livestock production, including donkey breeding, increases with fewer days spent in the barn. Donkeys are lovers of the open outdoors and thrive on open spaces. They graze well on free pastures. This raises the logical question of how they satisfy their water needs.

Picture 11. Lake with clean and fresh water, Stara Planina (Serbia) (Foto: M. Urošević)

In Central Europe, since ancient times, simple wells known as well ("đerams") were commonly used. Water was drawn from these wells and poured into troughs. Livestock would come to drink water from these troughs at specific times during the day. In flatland areas where water is relatively shallow

underground, simple constructions for drawing water from wells have been used historically and are still used today. The well walls must be lined with masonry to prevent soil collapse.

Picture 12. Well (đeram) of Sime Mijić, Bukovac, around 1900. (www.ravnoplov.rs/deram)

As seen in the photograph, the "đeram" features a wooden construction with two arms, a vertical and a horizontal one. The vertical arm is buried in the ground and serves as a support for the horizontal arm. At one end of the horizontal arm, typically a stone is used as a counterweight, while at the other end, a long pole is attached via a movable joint. At the end of this pole, there is a container for water. The length of this wooden pole must be sufficient to allow the water container to immerse into the water in the well.

The container is lowered into the well by pulling down on the arm. When the person drawing water sees that the container is filled, they release the arm. The counterbalance at the other end of the horizontal arm presses the arm downward, bringing the water container to the surface. The water can then be poured into containers or troughs for supplying donkeys or other livestock.

Picture 13. Well Sweep in Romania (Hielscher, cit. Nussbag, 1957)

Picture 14. Motif from Banat (Vojvodina, Serbia) (Group of authors, 2019)

This method of drawing water does not require electrical energy or a motor to operate. The capacity is not particularly large since the water container is not very big. Additionally, the livestock keeper must exert considerable effort daily to water the donkeys using this method. A much easier way to water donkeys is if there

is a watercourse passing through or near their pasture. It is crucial that the water is clean and fresh. A well must be secured to prevent livestock from falling into it. In the past, wooden fences were used, but more recently, concrete barriers have been implemented as protection.

Picture 15. Concrete protective barrier (foto: M.Urošević)

As already mentioned, the well is not deep in the case of a „đeram“ (a type of traditional well). To prevent the soil from collapsing into the water, the walls are lined with bricks.

Picture 16. Well wall (foto: M.Urošević)

Water is drawn from the well and poured into a concrete trough for watering. Naturally, all animals drink from this water, not just donkeys. In this case, the water stays in the trough, unlike in artesian wells where

water continuously flows and the excess overflows from the well. This makes the water significantly cleaner compared to the „đeram,“ where water remains

stagnant in the concrete trough. Therefore, the troughs in the „đeram“ must be cleaned from time to time.

Picture 17. A flatland pasture with a well („đeram“) next to which is a watering trough (foto: M.Urošević)

Cleaning the trough is solved in a very simple manner. At the opposite end from where the water is poured, there is a hole sealed with a wooden plug.

When needed, the plug is removed, the water drains out, fresh water is poured in, the trough is washed, and then the hole is closed again

Picture 18. Concrete watering trough with water (foto: M.Urošević)

Picture 19. Wooden plug at the end of the trough (foto.M.Urošević)

If there is a watercourse near or passing through the pasture, it's important that donkeys have easy access to the water. Sometimes, the banks of the watercourse can be slightly higher, preventing donkeys from reaching the water. In such cases, it's necessary to

excavate a bit of soil to create a gentle slope for easy access to the water. If the shoreline is not high, there is no need to create special access points to the water. Donkeys will naturally find the most convenient spots to approach the water and drink on their own.

Picture 20. Access to water constructed, Zasavica Nature Park, Serbia (foto:M.Urošević)

Picture 21. Watercourse in Transylvania (Romania) where donkeys drink water without the shoreline being prepared for their descent (Foto: M.Urošević)

Donkeys receive very high-quality water if there is access to artesian water on the pasture. Such water is fresh and clean, and donkeys willingly drink it. Watering is typically done from built troughs or water basins. Artesian water has a constant temperature, ranging between 5-12°C. However, the temperature of artesian water can vary significantly. These differences in temperature arise due to the influence of various geological factors, primarily the geothermal characteristics of the terrain. Artesian water can originate from both shallow and deep wells. Water from shallow wells, defined as those up to 100 meters

deep, typically has a temperature close to the surface temperature. In temperate climate regions, this range is 10-20°C. In contrast, deep wells, those over 100 meters deep, can bring water to the surface with higher temperatures. This variation depends on the geological characteristics and geothermal nature of the terrain. For every 100 meters of depth, the water temperature increases by up to 3°C. It is possible for such water to reach temperatures of 30°C or higher at the surface. Such water is not suitable for drinking.

Picture 22. Different water horizons: K1 – shallow, K2 – intermediate, K3 – deep (Onegov et al. 1977)

When the water is located deeper than what can be accessed with a traditional well sweep, a slightly different method is used. This system is still in use today and is known as a spindle (or winch) well. The mechanism for drawing water is quite simple. A round log is set on stands and is turned using a wheel. A water container is attached to a rope or chain. By turning the

wheel, the log rotates, unwinding the rope (or chain) and lowering the container into the water. Once the container is full, the wheel is turned in the opposite direction to raise the full container. The person operating the wheel then catches the container, lifts it, and pours the water into a trough. This method is suitable for watering a small number of animals.

Picture 23. Well on the winder, Crvena reka, Banat, Serbia, 1962. (Čakan, 2011)

When donkeys are watered from natural watercourses, it is important to consider that the self-purification process of water, in the case of pollution, occurs over a distance of 15 km from the source of contamination. Therefore, water is generally clean only

at a distance of 15 km from the pollution site. Fortunately, donkeys are very sensitive to water pollution. Practically speaking, if they approach and drink the water, it can be considered clean.

Picture 24. Donkeys at the watering trough, concrete basins filled with artesian water, Zasavica Nature Park, Serbia. (Foto: M. Urošević)

There are noticeable algae deposits on the water surface, but this does not deter the donkeys from drinking the water. In hilly terrain with multiple small watercourses, the flow from several of these smaller streams can be directed towards a watering trough. This

ensures there is always fresh, clean water available in sufficient quantities. In such areas, the principle of water catchment is often applied. If there are several smaller, weaker sources, their water is collected and directed towards the watering trough.

Picture 25. Donkey at a watering trough in the hilly terrain (Collection: S.Ličanin)

In harsh conditions like the steppes of Central Asia (Kazakhstan), donkeys do not always have access to water whenever they want. They often have to wait for

water to be distributed from a cistern to larger containers or barrels before they can drink.

Picture 26. On the steppe in Kazakhstan, a donkey waits for the water to reach the top of the barrel so it can drink. (Foto: M.Urošević)

Water can be delivered using water tanks equipped with drinking troughs. Donkeys quickly adapt to the

locations where such tanks are placed and come to drink water regularly.

Picture 27. Water tank with mounted drinking bowls (PPA-21.7) (Onegov et al. 1977)

An interesting situation occurs in Turkey (Anatolia) where guard dogs are tied to the donkey. As the donkey moves, so do the dogs. Neither the donkey

nor the dogs drink water unless they come across a clean puddle along the way, until they return home in the evening.

Picture 28. Water is only available at the end of the working day. Turkey (Anatolia) (Foto: M. Urošević)

During their time with the sheep in the pasture, moving as the sheep move, the donkey carries everything the shepherd needs. In the meadow, the donkey is allowed to graze but there is no water. If the

grass is lush, the donkey meets a significant portion of its water needs. When the sheep go to drink, the donkey, with all its load, waits until the sheep finish drinking before continuing the journey home.

Picture 29. On a good pasture, it does not drink water during the day. Turkey (Anatolia) (foto: M. Urošević)

Picture 30. The sheep are at the watering place, and the donkey is observing the surroundings. Turkey (Anatolia)
Foto: M. Urošević

Conclusion

Donkeys require fresh, organoleptically acceptable, clean water. If the water is dirty, they will not drink it and will remain thirsty. When fresh, juicy food is available, the amount of water needed is significantly reduced. They need 8-10 liters of water per 100 kg of body weight daily. Watering systems vary greatly depending on tradition and technical capabilities.

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